

The role of fans in sustainable sports development in European professional football: A systematic review on environmental sustainability

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Abstract

Fans are important stakeholders in football clubs. While they contribute significantly to carbon emissions, they also have the potential to act as ambassadors for sustainable development in society. Understanding fan behaviour is crucial for football clubs to develop effective and targeted sustainability measures. However, the role of fans has not yet been fully explored and a comprehensive view of fan behaviour in the context of environmental sustainability in European football is still lacking. To address this research gap a systematic literature review was conducted following the PRISMA Guidelines. The search was carried out in the Web of Science, SPORTDiscus, Scopus, Sage and SURF databases in February 2025. A total of 1180 articles were identified, where 30 articles met all inclusion criteria, which were: articles published in English between 2015 and 2025 and empirical research on fans, European professional/ semi-professional football and environmental sustainability. Non-empirical articles and studies that did not align with the research question were excluded. The methodological quality and risk of bias of the included studies were assessed using the Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool (MMAT). Based on the topics of the studies, the papers were grouped into three categories: (1) carbon emissions in football, (2) sustainability strategies of football clubs and (3) interactions between fans and clubs. Most of the existing research focuses on carbon emissions related to fan travel and mobility patterns. The results confirm that fans are key stakeholders who can implement sustainable behaviour in society. They can influence clubs, but clubs can also influence fans by acting as role models. Fans are not a homogeneous group, that's why sustainable fan behaviour varies by factors like age, team identification or knowledge of sustainability. Clubs should implement visible environmental actions within stadiums, using targeted communication and supporting sustainability initiatives that fit the club's identity and providing general education on environmental topics in fan's daily life. Effective communication should focus on collective efforts and positive-framed messages. Future research should focus on stronger cross-country collaboration, more studies in Eastern Europe and closer cooperation between researchers and football clubs.

Key Words: Fans, football, sustainable sports, climate change, carbon footprint, sustainability, sport ecology, pro-environmental behaviour, corporate social responsibility

1 Research context

The sport market is growing rapidly and it is expected to grow at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 5.6% from sales of \$506.93 billion to \$629.81 billion by 2028 (By Type, Revenue Source, Ownership, 2024). Such expansion presents major challenges for sports organizers, because they are required to aspire social responsibility and manage limited resources (Cerezo-Esteve et al., 2022). One critical area where this responsibility becomes evident is environmental sustainability, as sport has a complex relationship with the environment: On one hand it causes significant CO₂ emissions, whether through major events such as the Olympic Games or the Football World Cup (Thormann & Wicker, 2021; Tóffano Pereira et al., 2019). On the other hand sport is affected by the impacts of climate change and disciplines such as skiing are already feeling the consequences of it (Thormann & Wicker, 2021). This bidirectional relationship between sport and the environment shows how closely the two areas are intertwined and emphasizes the need for sustainable approaches in the sports sector (Bernard et al., 2021; Orr & Inoue, 2019). In the last years sport organizations have increasingly begun to commit to sustainable practices. Collaborations with institutions like the UN Climate Change Secretariat to achieve the Paris climate goals (*Sports Representatives and the UN Pitch for Climate Action I UNFCCC*, 2017) and initial approaches such as climate-friendly events and sustainable catering are increasingly being implemented in the sport sector (Trendafilova et al., 2013).

There are already numerous studies on environmental sustainability in American professional sports (Cury et al., 2023), which is why authors such as Wall-Tweedie & Nguyen (2018) are calling for research in other geographical areas. This paper ties in with this by focusing on the analysis of environmental sustainability in European football. The focus on European football is intentional, as it is highly relevant to society in all European countries and enables comparable analyses and results thanks to a standardized set of rules. Moreover, many studies have focused on the ecological impact of mega-sporting events (Cerezo-Esteve et al., 2022; González-Serrano et al., 2020), which is according to Mascarenhas et al. (2021) due to external pressure. The environmental impacts of mega-sporting events are significant but limited in time (Daddi et al., 2024). Football matches, on the other hand, take place weekly or several times a week. The enormous frequency and increasing popularity of football is leading to a high and continuously growing carbon footprint of the sport (Tóffano Pereira et al., 2019). This development is intensified by an increasing expansion strategy in football: for example, the men's football World Cup has been expanded from 32 to 48 teams and new competitions such as the UEFA Europa Conference League have been launched (Gammelsæter & Loland, 2023). Although the contribution of football clubs to the global carbon footprint has been recognized, there is still a lack of systematic assessment of these impacts (Tóffano Pereira et al., 2019).

Fans are a key driver of CO₂ emissions, as significant amounts of CO₂ are released as a result of travelling to and from matches, buying merchandise or consuming food in stadiums (Jaehne, 2024). However, the role of fans in sustainable sports development has been insufficiently explored (Daddi et al., 2024). Authors such as Martins et al. (2021) or Mascarenhas et al. (2021) are calling for the role of spectators to be better understood, particularly because sport can serve as a role model for environmentally friendly behaviour (Inoue & Kent, 2012). Clubs and organizations can exert considerable influence on fans and encourage them to adopt sustainable behaviours in their everyday lives (Blankenbuehler & Kunz, 2014). So far, there are studies that examine individual aspects of fan behaviour in football, for example how spectators travel to and from matches (Loewen & Wicker, 2021; Thormann & Wicker, 2024). However, a holistic view of fans and their behavioural patterns is missing, which could be because research on the link between climate change and sports has so far

been highly fragmented with studies published in different journals and disciplines (Orr et al., 2022; Wilby et al., 2023). The interest of this research is to combine the literature from the various fields and to obtain a better overview of the topic. This will not only enable a better contextual understanding of the existing individual studies but also create a solid foundation for targeting future research and promoting sustainable strategies in the sports environment. Furthermore, the paper will provide a valuable basis for clubs and organizations to develop effective strategies to bring fans to more pro-environmental behaviour. By focusing on how clubs can encourage such behaviour and act as agents of change for millions of fans, this literature review provides an important foundation for future research and practical strategies to enhance environmental sustainability in sport.

2 Methods

2.1 Search strategy

The databases SPORTDiscus, Web of Science, Scopus, Sage and SURF were selected for the literature research. SPORTDiscus and SURF were considered, because they are specifically tailored towards sports science research. As multidisciplinary, renowned databases, Web of Science and Scopus offer broad scientific coverage and are essential for a systematic review. In addition, Sage was included as it contains numerous social science and environmental studies relevant to sustainable behaviour in sport. In addition, a manual search was conducted in scientific journals that are considered particularly relevant to the research field. Further articles were also manually searched for on the Internet (platforms such as ResearchGate or Google Scholar). This comprehensive search strategy ensures that a holistic view of fans and their behaviour is captured. The entire search process was conducted accordance with the PRISMA Guidelines (Page et al., 2021). The PRIMSA Flow Chart and the PRISMA Checklist were applied to ensure transparency, replicability and reporting quality.

The 'PICO scheme' was used to identify the central keywords for the search terms (Nordhausen & Hirt, 2022). The keywords 'fan', 'sustainable sports' and 'football' were derived from the research question (What role do fans play in promoting environmental sustainability in European professional football and in sustainable development in general?). Synonyms for these keywords were researched and then combined using the Boolean operators AND and OR as well as truncation symbols to create comprehensive search terms (Bartels, 2013). For example, terms such as green sport, green travel and green economy were combined under the truncation term 'green*'. The search terms were adapted several times and checked for accuracy in close collaboration with a fellow student and the supervisor. Care was also taken to ensure that the search strings were adapted individually for each database, as not all databases support the same Boolean operators. This explains why the individual databases can have minimally different search terms.

The final search in the databases was carried out with a single-line search term (table 1) on February 10, 2025. The search in the databases was limited to a search in the abstract, as otherwise too many results would come up and it would go beyond the scope of the work. In addition, a manual search for further articles was carried out on February 11, 2025. The methodological procedure and the detailed documentation of the search were recorded in a search protocol to present the procedure transparently and make it repeatable at any time.

Table 1: Boolean search term for Web of Science

Keywords	Search terms
Fans	(FAN* OR SUPPORTER* OR ENTHUSIAST* OR ULTRA* OR CONSUMER* OR STAKEHOLDER* OR SPECTATOR* OR FOLLOWER*)
	AND
Sustainable sports	(SUSTAINABILITY OR SUSTAINABLE* OR "SPORT ECOLOGY" OR CSR OR ENVIRONMENTAL* OR GREEN* OR ECO* OR LOW-IMPACT OR CARBON-NEUTRAL OR "ZERO WASTE" OR "CO2 EMISSIONS" OR "CARBON FOOTPRINT" OR "CLIMATE CHANGE")
	AND
Football	("PROFESSIONAL SPORT" OR FOOTBALL OR "EUROPEAN FOOTBALL" OR UEFA OR "CHAMPIONS LEAGUE" OR "FOOTBALL LEAGUE" OR "PREMIER LEAGUE" OR LALIGA OR "SERIA A" OR BUNDESLIGA OR "LIGUE 1")

2.2 Screening process

A sensitive search principle was used for the systematic literature analysis in order to identify as many relevant studies as possible. The aim of this comprehensive search was to provide a detailed overview of the current state of the literature and to ensure that no relevant articles were overlooked (Nordhausen & Hirt, 2022). The inclusion and exclusion criteria were then defined (table 2). Only articles published between 2015 and 2025 and written in English were considered. Publications without empirical research, including books, book chapters, conference papers or dissertations were excluded. Studies that focused on regions outside Europe or examined sports other than football were not included. Furthermore, all articles that exclusively addressed social sustainability were excluded as this study specifically investigates environmental sustainability in professional football. Similarly, studies that did not identify fans as a central target group were not considered, as their role in sustainable sports development is the primary focus of this analysis. Both professional and semi-professional football were considered, although the main emphasis was placed on the professional level.

Table 2: Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Inclusion	Exclusion
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Journal articles, written in English Published between 2015 and 2025 Professional and semi-professional football Articles related to European Football, Fans and environmental sustainability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Studies that do not align with the research question Studies without empirical research (Books, Dissertations...) Full-text not available

The entire screening process was carried out using the Covidence platform (*Covidence - Better Systematic Review Management*, 2025). Once all articles have been identified (n = 1180), the duplicates were first sorted out. The remaining articles were then screened based on their title and abstract. To ensure the traceability of the screening process, the respective reason for exclusion was documented in an Excel sheet for each excluded article. This left 64 articles for the full-text analysis. The full texts could be obtained for all studies, meaning that no additional titles had to be excluded in this phase. Further studies were eliminated during the full-text analysis. The most common reasons were that the studies did not deal with environmental sustainability, were not related to European professional football or did not examine the role of fans. After this final screening process, 30

studies met all inclusion criteria and were included in the analysis. The entire screening process and the number of excluded and included studies are shown in detail in the Prisma flow chart (figure 1).

Figure 1: PRISMA flow chart of article identification and screening (from: Page et al., 2021)

2.3 Data extraction and analysis

The analysis consisted of a descriptive and a thematic summary of the literature. The selection of the descriptive characteristics was based on methodological recommendations from literature review research (Booth et al., 2012). These features – such as authorship, year, journal, study design, country context and sample characteristics – are considered essential to ensure transparency, comparability and replicability in literature reviews. The PRISMA 2020 checklist explicitly recommends reporting key study characteristics to support the reproducibility and clarity of systematic syntheses (Page et al., 2021). In addition, other reviews were examined to find further interesting descriptive points of analysis. This search resulted in the analysis of the following ten categories: (1) study, (2),

authors, (3) year of publication, (4) journal, (5) key words, (6) country of study, (7) football club, (8) theories, (9) study type, (10) participants of studies.

After the descriptive analysis of the papers, thematic coding was carried out. This involved categorizing the content of the articles and identifying specific topics and subcategories. An integrative approach was pursued that new perspectives, patterns and connections became visible (Torraco, 2005). Previous studies emphasized that integrative reviews are particularly suitable for topics where – as in the case of football and climate change – a growing but heterogeneous knowledge base already exists. Furthermore, the process of thematic categorization followed an inductive coding approach (Saldaña, 2021) and was carried out iteratively, allowing the refinement of existing categories and the addition of new sub-themes where necessary. In the analysis section, the articles were evaluated within the groups and the main findings of each article were compared in Excel.

Since this review includes a mix of quantitative and qualitative studies, the Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool (MMAT) was used to assess methodological quality (Hong et al., 2018). Reviews were not evaluated methodologically, as they do not present original empirical studies. The MMAT criteria can be rated as 'Yes' (fulfilled), 'No' (not fulfilled), 'Unclear' (U) or 'Not applicable' (N/A). To facilitate comparison, an overall quality score from 1 to 5 was assigned to each included study. Studies with a score of 5 were classified as high quality, scores of 3 and 4 as moderate quality and scores of 1 or 2 as low quality. A color-coded traffic light system (green = high, yellow = moderate, red = low quality) was used to visually represent the methodological risk of bias across the included studies.

3 Results

3.1 Descriptive analysis

The 30 identified articles were published in a total of 26 different journals, with the most articles published in the journal *Sustainability* (n = 3), followed by *Journal of Strategic Marketing and Sport Management Review* (with two articles each). The use of a wide variety of journals shows that the subject area is broadly diversified and that the sensitive research principle therefore made sense. This is in line with the statement by Orr et al. (2022) and Wilby et al. (2023), who found that the relationship between climate change and sport has so far been very fragmented and that the studies have so far been published in a wide variety of journals. This can also be seen in the keywords. A total of 91 different keywords were used. The words football (n = 10), sustainability (n = 9), climate change (n = 6), sport ecology (n = 5), pro-environmental behaviour (n = 4), consumer behaviour (n = 4) and CSR (n = 4) were used most frequently. In addition, the word sustainable was combined five times with another word (e.g. sustainable consumption), as environmental (n = 4) and pro-environmental (n = 3). It was noticeable that the word behaviour was used very frequently but the British and the American writing was used (behavior vs. behaviour). The word fan was used less frequently, whereas consumer behaviour was used more often. A look at the publication years of the studies shows that only a few studies on this topic were published between 2015 and 2020. After 2021/2022, the number of publications increased sharply, indicating that the research field is new, very current and of great interest (figure 2). A look at the first authors shows that Cayolla has published most studies with four. Looking at all authors together, Daddi (n = 5), Cayolla (n = 5), Wicker (n = 5) and McCullough (n = 4) are the most frequently published researchers in this field.

Figure 2: Number of publications per year

The next step was to examine which countries and football clubs were researched in the individual studies. It was noticeable that almost half of all individual country-specific studies were conducted in Germany (n = 7) and England (n = 6). In addition, there are some studies in Southern Europe (e.g. Portugal (n = 4), whereas no individual studies on the topic have been published in Eastern Europe until now. Among the papers that specifically dealt with one football club, FC Porto and Forest Green Rovers were the most frequently analysed, with four studies each. In addition, multinational studies were conducted in four papers, in which countries in Eastern Europe were also examined for the first time. Particularly multinational research was conducted in the studies of the Europe Tackle project, which included participants from a lot of different countries. For the illustration Europe was divided into Northern, Eastern, Southern and Western Europe according to the United Nations (Nations Unies, 1999). Turkey was included in the analysis because it is part of UEFA (figure 3).

Figure 3: Geographical distribution of studies on football, fans and environmental sustainability: national vs. multinational research

Quantitative studies represent the majority, with a total of 15 studies or 50% of the total. The second most common were qualitative studies with 11, representing 37%, followed by mixed-methods designs with four articles, which corresponds to 13%. Fans were examined most frequently in the context of surveys (n = 13) and only three times in qualitative studies. The other studies, for example, interviewed managers, analysed websites and documents or conducted a literature search.

In the next step the papers were reviewed and categorized into preliminary thematic categories. As a result, three main themes were identified (table 3): (a) Carbon emissions in football; (b) Sustainability strategies of football clubs; (c) Interactions between fans and clubs. In addition, nine subcategories were identified.

Table 3: Categorization of research papers by main topics and subtopics

Theme	Sub-themes	Articles
Carbon emissions in football	Overall carbon footprint (clubs & fans)	(Khanna et al., 2024)
	Fan-related environmental behaviour and carbon emissions:	
	Transportation and emissions from travel	(Cayolla, Quintela, et al., 2023; Dosumu et al., 2017; Herold et al., 2024; Konstantopoulos et al., 2024; Loewen & Wicker, 2021; Thormann et al., 2022)
	Fan mobility and environmental behaviour: travel choices & environmental awareness	(Marrucci et al., 2024; Thormann & Wicker, 2024; Zitzke et al., 2023) (Scharfenkamp & Wicker, 2024; Pape et al., 2023, 2024; Scharfenkamp, 2024)
Sustainability strategies of football clubs	Stadium consumption behaviour: merchandising, food, waste behaviour	
	Analysis of sustainability strategies	(Grabowski, 2021; Lobillo Mora et al., 2021; Lozano & Barreiro-Gen, 2023; Samuel et al., 2024)
Interactions between fans and clubs	Stakeholders' pressure on football clubs	(Cayolla et al., 2024; Daddi et al., 2021; Sonmezoglu, 2016; Todaro, 2023)
	Environmental communication	(Amann & Doidge, 2023; Gionfriddo et al., 2023; Wagan, 2024)
	Sustainable behaviour as a driver of social change	(Cayolla, Escadas, Biscaia, et al., 2023; Cayolla, Escadas, Mccullough, et al., 2023; Delia et al., 2024; Mabon, 2023; Samuel et al., 2022)

The thematic analysis of the 30 studies shows that nearly half of the studies (n = 14) can be assigned to the area of carbon emissions in football, with a particular focus on fans' transportation and sustainable travel behaviour (n = 9). Approximately one third of the studies (n = 12) address interactions between fans and clubs, including stakeholder influences and sustainable behaviour. Only four studies examine the sustainability strategies of football clubs and investigate which measures are implemented to promote sustainable behaviour among fans (figure 4).

Figure 4: Thematic allocation of the studies

3.2 Analysis of studies

As described in section 2.3, all included studies were assessed using the Mixed-Methods Appraisal Tool (MMAT). Overall, 9 studies were rated with high quality, 17 with moderate quality and three with low quality (table 4). The distribution was as follows:

- Qualitative studies: 7 = high, 2 = moderate, 1 = low
- Quantitative studies: 15 = moderate
- Mixed-method studies: 2 = high, 2 = low

The distribution indicates that there is still considerable room for improvement in the methodological quality of the current research landscape. One notable pattern is that none of the quantitative studies achieved a high-quality ranking. A key reason for this is the consistent lack of transparency regarding participant exclusion. Not a single study provided clear information on the number of participants excluded, the reasons for exclusion or demographic details of those excluded. This lack of information increases the potential for nonresponse bias and limits the interpretability and generalizability of the results.

Table 4: methodological assessment of the studies

Studies						Rating	Quality evaluation
QUALITATIVE STUDIES	Is the qualitative approach appropriate to answer the research question?	Are the qualitative data collection methods adequate to address the research question?	Are the findings adequately derived from the data?	Is the interpretation of results sufficiently substantiated by data?	Is there coherence between qualitative data sources, collection, analysis and interpretation?		
(Wagan, 2024)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	5	high
(Lozano & Barreiro-Gen, 2023)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	5	high
(Grabowski, 2021)	Unclear	Unclear	Unclear	Unclear	Unclear	0	low
(Delia et al., 2024)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	5	high
(Samuel et al., 2022)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	5	high
(Amann & Doidge, 2023)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	5	high
(Samuel et al., 2024)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	5	high
(Sonmezoglu, 2016)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Unclear	3	moderate
(Zitzke et al., 2023)	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Unclear	Yes	3	moderate
(Cayolla et al., 2024)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	5	high

QUANTITATIVE STUDIES	Is the sampling strategy relevant to address the research question?	Is the sample representative of the target population?	Are the measurements appropriate?	Is the risk of nonresponse bias low?	Is the statistical analysis appropriate to answer the research question?		
(Scharfenkamp & Wicker, 2024)	Yes	No	Yes	Unclear	Yes	3	moderate
(Cayolla, Escadas, Mccullough, et al., 2023)	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Unclear	Yes	3	moderate
(Scharfenkamp, 2024)	Yes	No	Yes	Unclear	Yes	3	moderate
(Daddi et al., 2021)	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Unclear	Yes	3	moderate
(Loewen & Wicker, 2021)	Yes	No	Yes	Unclear	Yes	3	moderate
(Thormann & Wicker, 2024)	Yes	No	Yes	Unclear	Yes	3	moderate
(Konstantopoulos et al., 2024)	Yes	No	Yes	Unclear	Yes	3	moderate
(Marrucci et al., 2024)	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Unclear	Yes	3	moderate
(Dosumu et al., 2017)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Yes	4	moderate
(Todaro, 2023)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Yes	4	moderate
(Thormann et al., 2022)	Yes	No	Yes	Unclear	Yes	3	moderate
(Cayolla, Quintela, et al., 2023)	Yes	No	Yes	Unclear	Yes	3	moderate
(Gionfriddo et al., 2023)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Unclear	Yes	4	moderate
(Herold et al., 2024)	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Unclear	Yes	3	moderate
(Cayolla, Escadas, Biscaia, et al., 2023)	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Unclear	Yes	3	moderate
MIXED-METHOD STUDIES	Is there an adequate rationale for using a mixed methods design to address the research question?	Are the different components of the study effectively integrated to answer the research question?	Are the outputs of the integration of qualitative and quantitative components adequately interpreted?	Are divergences and inconsistencies between quantitative and qualitative results adequately addressed?	Do the different components of the study adhere to the quality criteria of each tradition of the methods involved?		
(Pape et al., 2023)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	5	high
(Pape et al., 2024)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	5	high
(Lobillo Mora et al., 2021)	Yes	Unclear	Unclear	Yes	No	2	low
(Khanna et al., 2024)	Yes	Unclear	Unclear	Yes	No	2	low

3.2.1 Carbon emissions in football

Khanna et al. (2024) conducted the first comprehensive carbon footprint assessment of a professional European football club using a participatory action research approach. The study reveals that the majority of greenhouse gas emissions (72%) at sport events stem from indirect sources (Scope 3), with fan transportation alone accounting for 38% of total emissions. Energy consumption within the club's facilities (Scope 2) represents the second largest source, contributing 22.5% to the overall footprint. While Khanna et al. (2024) provide a holistic assessment of a football club's carbon footprint, subsequent studies have focused more narrowly on specific emission sources. Four of the studies focused on the fan-related emissions through transportation and calculated the CO₂e emissions of fans per match. While Loewen & Wicker (2021) calculated an average of 27.6 kg CO₂e per fan per match in Germany, Dosumu et al. (2017) reported only 4.74 kg CO₂e per fan per match in England. The significantly lower emissions in the study by Dosumu et al. (2017) can be explained primarily by the inclusion of lower leagues (tiers 3-10), which generate significantly lower CO₂e emissions than professional clubs due to shorter travel distances and lower spectator numbers. Professional clubs cause higher emissions overall, particularly due to longer distances and a larger fan base (Dosumu et al., 2017). In England and Portugal, the majority of fans used the car to get to the stadium, while in the German and Austrian studies most of the fans used public transportation to get there. However, all studies consistently show that car travel contributes the largest share of total emissions - in all cases approximately 70%. The demographic composition of the samples was also consistent: In all studies, that reported the distribution of gender, the majority of respondents were male (74% to 92%) and middle-aged (between 32 and 42 years).

Table 5: Summary of key findings from studies on transportation and emissions from travel

Study	Country / Liga	Sample	Gender distribution/ mean age	Included match types	Mode of transport (%)	CO ₂ emissions (Fan / match)
Dosumu et al., 2017	England (Tier 3-10)	1.649 Fans	80% male, 20% female ø 42 years	Home / away matches	Car: 67.5%, public transportation: 17.8 %, walking: 13.4%, others: 1.3%	Ø 4.74 kg CO ₂ e (70% of that from car travel)
Loewen & Wicker, 2021	Germany (Bundesliga, all clubs)	539 Fans	92% male, 8% female Ø 32.7 years	Home / away matches	Car: 36.1%, airplane: 0.7%, public transportation: 49.4%, coach: 7.7%, walk/ bicycle: 6.2%	Ø 27.8 kg CO ₂ e (70.3% of that from car travel)
Herold et al., 2024	Austria (Rapid Vienna)	3.317 Fans	/ Ø 35-40 years	Home games	Car: 42.5%, public transportation 52.8%, bike/ walking: 3.7%, others: 0.9%	Ø 6.0 kg CO ₂ e (71.6% of that from car travel)
Thormann et al., 2022	Germany (Arminia Bielefeld)	1.605 Fans	74.3 % male, 25.7% female; ø 32.4 years	Home games	Car: 20.8%, public transportation: 49.2%, walking: 25.4%, bicycle: 3.9%, others: 0.7%	Ø 7.79 kg CO ₂ e (75.3% of that from car travel)
(Cayolla, Quintela, et al. (2023)	Portugal (FC Porto)	5.694 Fans	/	Home games	Car: 66%, public transportation: 23.5%, 5.1% vehicles with environmentally friendly energies	/
Konstantopoulos et al., 2024	Greece (Greece vs. Ireland)	578	79% male, 21% female; 53% < 25 years	One UEFA match	Car: 55%, metro: 23%, buses: 14%	/

Herold et al. (2024) and Cayolla, Quintela, et al. (2023) both show that the distance to the stadium has a central influence on the choice of means of transport: the further the journey, the more frequently the car is used. Herold et al. (2024) found that holders of an annual public transport ticket use public transport more frequently and that gender-specific differences exist in mobility behaviour. These gender effects were confirmed by Konstantopoulos et al. (2024), who reported that while 55% of all respondents travelled by car, the proportion was significantly higher among female fans (64.2%) compared to male fans (52.9%), supporting earlier findings by Herold et al. (2024) (37.3% vs. 31.4%). In addition, female fans also showed a significantly greater willingness to engage in environmental actions, highlighting a consistent gender differences in both mobility behaviour and

environmental engagement (Konstantopoulos et al. 2024). The study by Cayolla, Quintela, et al. (2023) examined the use of sustainable energy in the arrival and departure of fans: 95% of fans who used car used fossil fuels (76% diesel, 19% petrol) and only 1.3% of vehicles used clean energy. On average, there were 2.72 people per vehicle, with car occupancy increasing with distance. Fans living closer to the stadium were more likely to travel on foot.

Beyond that, several studies have examined the motivations behind fans' choice of transportation to football matches. Convenience emerged as the dominant reason for transport decisions across all studies. In the study by Konstantopoulos et al. (2024), 66% of fans identified convenience as their primary reason for choosing a specific mode of transport, followed by time efficiency (30%) and comfort (20%). Only 7% mentioned environmental consciousness as a determinant. These findings align with the earlier research by Loewen & Wicker (2021), who also found that comfort, cost and habit were among the main drivers of transport behaviour, while environmental awareness had no significant effect on the choice of transport mode, clearly illustrating the value-action gap. Similarly, Thormann & Wicker (2024) applied rational choice theory to explain fan mobility decisions. Their results confirmed that fans weigh perceived benefits and costs when selecting how to travel to the stadium. Perceived benefits such as avoiding overcrowded trains, enjoying fresh air or acting as a role model increased the probability of choosing environmentally friendly options like bicycles or e-scooters. However, perceived costs, including longer travel times or unavailability of the same transport after the match, acted as significant barriers. The distance to the stadium was found to be the strongest negative predictor for sustainable choices in all tested models. In a broader context, Thormann et al. (2022) found that environmentally friendly behaviour, such as recycling or using public transport, was positively associated with life satisfaction and happiness, suggesting that sustainable choices can contribute to the subjective well-being of stadium visitors. Furthermore Loewen & Wicker (2021) found that social characteristics such as club membership and fan loyalty had a far greater influence on emissions than environmental awareness. Fans with strong club identification travelled longer distances and attended more matches, leading to significantly higher emissions. Club members produced around four times as much CO₂ as non-members. Also, Marrucci et al. (2024) explored the psychological and social aspects and found that attitudes and social norms were the strongest predictors of fans' intention to use sustainable transport. Although there are predominantly positive intentions among fans, these only lead to sustainable behaviour under certain conditions. The main barriers are a lack of mobility information, the limited influence of clubs on public transport and time and financial barriers for fans. In this context, Zitzke et al. (2023) emphasize the important role of football clubs as institutional actors who, through strategic partnerships and visible commitment, can help reduce such structural barriers and promote more sustainable mobility practices among fans.

In addition, four studies were identified that focus on the consumption behaviour of football fans, one on sustainable merchandising and three on food behaviour in stadiums. Scharfenkamp & Wicker (2024) examined football fans' willingness to pay (WTP) for sustainably produced fan merchandise using a T-shirt and a hoodie as examples. While 57.1% of respondents indicated a positive WTP, average values were higher for hoodies (65.50€) than for T-shirts (29.86€). However, overall interest was greater for the lower-priced item. Higher WTP was associated with environmental concern, interest in sustainability labels, prior merchandise purchases and regular stadium attendance. Team identification increased general interest but was negatively related to WTP for more expensive items, suggesting that highly identified fans may support their clubs in other ways.

Three additional studies examined specific factors influencing plant-based consumption behaviour among football fans. The case study by Pape et al. (2023) on the Forest Green Rovers shows that

the internalization of team values has a significant positive effect on fans' intention to adopt a plant-based diet. Through the club's consistent vegan orientation and targeted internal communication, value processes were initiated, leading to a long-term shift in fans' dietary behaviour. In a comparative study Pape et al. (2024) demonstrated that the perceived match between fan and team personality is a central factor influencing plant-based consumption. For fans who don't feel strongly connected to the team, thinking the team has a better personality can lead to negative behaviour, even if they care a lot about sustainability. The study by Scharfenkamp (2024) investigates gender-specific differences in environmental awareness and everyday pro-environmental nutrition. Women report significantly higher levels of environmental concern and, when environmentally conscious, are more likely than men to follow a vegetarian or vegan diet in daily life. Regardless of environmental concern, women also show significantly higher interest in vegan food options at stadiums, especially vegan sausages or burgers. Surprisingly, vegetarian individuals show lower interest in vegan stadium options, contradicting previous assumptions that vegetarians are generally more open to vegan offerings. As only environmentally conscious women tend to eat vegan food regularly, offering both vegetarian and vegan alternatives at stadiums appears to be a smart solution.

3.2.2 Sustainability strategies of football clubs

The sustainable transformation of football clubs is increasingly part of strategic organizational development in professional football. The involvement of fans as stakeholders plays a central role in this. The four studies analysed, Borussia Dortmund (Grabowski, 2021), Real Betis Balompie' (Lobillo Mora et al., 2021), Forest Green Rovers (Samuel et al., 2024) and Swedish clubs (Lozano & Barreiro-Gen, 2023) show different strategic approaches.

Borussia Dortmund sees sustainable development as part of its corporate strategy, whereby economic, ecological and social responsibility are pursued in an integrated manner (Grabowski, 2021). Their management takes its social responsibility towards fans, club members, the city of Dortmund and the surrounding region into account, particularly through educational, environmental and inclusion projects. This research highlights that sustainable development should be an integral part of football clubs' management strategies, as it offers significant opportunities for economic growth and brand enhancement, exemplified by Borussia Dortmund, which ranks 12th among European football brands and first in Germany. Real Betis Balompie' is also pursuing a holistic CSR approach with its Forever Green program, which is characterized by rebranding and culture-changing processes. The study shows that fans have a predominantly positive perception of the club's commitment and recognize the connection between environmental responsibility, club image and a strengthened sense of pride in being part of the club (Lobillo Mora et al., 2021). Nevertheless, the direct involvement of fans in concrete sustainability measures remains low. Only 5% of those surveyed have actively participated. Communication takes place primarily via internal club media and social networks, which increases awareness but does not automatically increase engagement. The study of Samuel et al. (2024) focuses on the Forest Green Rovers and its pioneering role in terms of sustainable football. A key element of their success is the use of boundary objects that connect different stakeholder groups, including fans. Elements such as 'attractive football' or 'eco trail information boards' not only serve to convey information but also generate emotional loyalty and acceptance. At the same time, a key risk is pointed out: a decline in sporting performance may lead to fans' disillusionment with the club's environmental and social initiatives, what will weak their support and engagement. This could ultimately reduce the fanbase and undermine the long-term success of sustainability efforts. Finally, Lozano & Barreiro-Gen (2023) underline the long-term potential of football clubs to promote social change through their fan base. The Swedish clubs surveyed see fan identification as a key resource

for sustainable transformation, as shared identity can be a strong driver for making societies more sustainable. At the same time, there are deficits in environmental expertise and infrastructural framework conditions, such as stadium ownership or waste management. The study emphasizes the need to actively involve fans in measures - as recipients and as co-creators.

3.2.3 Interactions between fans and clubs

In professional football clubs interact with a wide range of stakeholders. Understanding the dynamics of the club-fan relationship is crucial, as influence can be exerted mutually: fans can exert pressure on clubs, while clubs can also shape fan behaviour and attitudes.

Cayolla et al. (2024), Daddi et al. (2021), Sonmezoglu (2016) and Todaro (2023) examine how fans can exert influence on the club and thereby promote sustainable measures. Cayolla et al. (2024) investigate the sustainability-related expectations of fans in professional sport and identify five overarching areas in which supporters believe clubs should improve: sustainable venue design eco-friendly matchday operations, green sponsorship activation, environmental communication and overall matchday experience. Fans made concrete suggestions such as improving public transportation (e.g. ecological shuttles), expanding vegetarian and vegan food options in stadium catering or banning smoking from all areas. Among all initiatives, renewable energy consistently emerged as the most highly valued, followed by waste reduction, improved waste management and recycling. These suggestions are closely linked to operational environmental practices, which are directly experienced on matchdays and thus more tangible to fans. As Todaro et al. (2023) emphasize, the influence of fans is particularly strong in these areas, while governance-related actions, such as environmental management systems or sustainability reporting, remain less visible for fans. Daddi et al. (2021) interpret this influence through the lens of institutional theory and highlight normative pressure as a key driver. Such pressure includes emerging social expectations, for instance the widespread use of reusable cups at football events. Normative pressure, as illustrated in both Daddi et al. (2021) and Cayolla et al. (2024), reflects fans' increasing demand for visible and tangible sustainability efforts. But fans can also use coercive pressure when clubs fail to meet environmental expectations, for example, by publicly criticizing or boycotting them. Fans can also exert pressure on clubs through their own organizations. The active role of fan organizations in CSR initiatives, as observed by Sonmezoglu (2016), further underlines their potential to not only demand but also implement sustainability practices. These bottom-up activities contribute positively to the club's image, strengthen supporter loyalty and raise public awareness. Fans, therefore, act both as critical voices and as proactive agents of change.

But also football clubs have the potential to influence fan behaviour and act as drivers for social change (Mabon, 2023). Empirical evidence supports that fans' positive perceptions of a club's environmental sustainability initiatives lead to increased environmental awareness and behaviour. Cayolla, Escadas, Biscaia, et al. (2023) find that club-led sustainability initiatives can positively influence fans' everyday decisions, such as recycling or reducing meat consumption. Particularly, a stronger pro-environmental attitude is associated with more frequent environmentally friendly behaviours in daily activities and consumption (Cayolla, Escadas, Mccullough, et al., 2023). But the type of consumer plays an important role. Emotionally involved sport fans reported higher levels of pro-environmental attitude and pro-environmental behavior (Cayolla, Escadas, Mccullough, et al., 2023). Therefore, strengthening fans' intrinsic pro-environmental attitudes should be a key goal for organizations (Cayolla, Escadas, Mccullough, et al., 2023). Moreover, fans can be inspired by their club's environmental initiatives and carry this inspiration into their social environments by e.g. talking with their friends and families about it (Cayolla, Escadas, Biscaia, et al., 2023; Delia et al., 2024). A

prominent example is the club Forest Green Rovers, where supporters reported that their affiliation with the club inspired them to make pro-environmental changes in their personal lives. This includes e.g. adopting plant-based diets or promoting environmental issues within their communities (Delia et al., 2024; Samuel et al., 2022). Another channel through which football may influence fans is the players themselves. Public figures in football are increasingly using their platforms to speak out on environmental issues, driven not only by personal concern but also by the growing impact of climate change on their sports. Initiatives such as Football Ecologie France aim to improve climate literacy among players, empowering them to act as climate ambassadors and contribute to wider societal change (Mabon, 2023).

Furthermore, the way in which environmental communication is implemented in professional football clubs is crucial. Collective behavior plays a central role in how football fans engage with environmental issues. Amann & Doidge (2023) show that football fans can act as a powerful collective force for addressing climate change, particularly when environmental communication aligns with their identity, worldview and the broader culture of football fandom. Their analysis of the Pledgeball campaign shows how football fans can be motivated to take climate action when they feel part of team effort. Fans were asked to make anonymous pledges to reduce CO₂ emissions. These were added up and compared with pledges from rival fan groups, turning it into a competition. This helped fans see the impact they can have together and made climate action feel like part of their role as supporters. Similarly, Gionfriddo et al. (2023) emphasize the influence of emotional and collective dynamics within stadium environments. Their findings reveal that fans respond more positively to environmental messages that highlight collective gains and pride, rather than guilt or neutrality. Stadiums are emotionally charged spaces where fans operate within a strong collective identity, which makes them more receptive to messages that resonate with shared values. However, this collective focus can also lead to behavioral inertia, as positive attitudes toward sustainability do not automatically result in concrete actions during matches. To overcome this gap Gionfriddo et al. (2023) recommend aligning the club's environmental efforts with those of its supporters and complementing communication with long-term educational and role-model strategies, especially outside the stadium context. In addition, they emphasize that environmental values and perceived environmental knowledge significantly enhance messages effectiveness, particularly when fans are able to step out of the collective matchday identity and reflect on their individual impact. Complementing these insights Cayolla et al. (2024) stress that raising awareness is the foundational step toward behavioral change. Their study highlights the importance of clear, continuous communication across all available platforms. They highlight platforms such as stadium videoboards, social media, newsletters and club TV and demand clubs not only to present their sustainability initiatives but also to communicate their outcomes. When fans are well-informed and see tangible results, they are more likely to support and adopt pro-environmental behaviors. This underscores the relevance that the type of message as well as the communication channels are important to change fan behavior. Wagan (2024) examines how different institutions talk about environmental issues in football. His analysis shows that organizations like FIFA and UEFA focus on a message that links sustainability to new technologies and small, gradual changes, while still supporting economic growth. In contrast, non-governmental organizations (NGOs) like 'We play Green' call for more radical changes and criticize the economic focus often found in mainstream environmental messages. Wagan (2024) shows that powerful organizations influence which views on the environment are accepted and which are pushed aside. This shapes how clubs and fans talk about sustainability. He argues that we need a more open and democratic discussion to prevent one-sided, profit-focused ideas of environmental responsibility.

4 Discussion

4.1 Interpretation of results

The results of the analysis clearly indicate that football fans do not present a homogenous group. They differ significantly in terms of environmental awareness and behavioural patterns. The following section considers key differentiating characteristics that are particularly relevant for sustainable fan behaviour: gender, age, team identification, environmental awareness & environmental communication.

Gender-based behavioural differences: Male and female fans show notable behavioural differences. According to several studies, women generally display higher environmental awareness and report more frequent environmentally friendly behaviour in everyday life, such as recycling, waste avoidance or purchasing recyclable products (Konstantopoulos et al., 2024; Scharfenkamp, 2024). They also show significantly greater interest in vegetarian and vegan stadium food options. At the same time, however, they are more likely to use cars for travelling to matches (Herold et al., 2024; Konstantopoulos et al., 2024), which may be influenced by structural or social factors such as perceived safety. The findings suggest that while women tend to be more willing to act sustainably, targeted structural support and communication strategies are needed to unlock this potential. Men, on the other hand, demonstrate lower behavioural intent, underlining the importance of persuasive and tailored environmental communication for this group.

Age-based behavioural differences: Age also proves to be a relevant factor. Older fans, on average, show higher levels of environmental engagement, particularly in concrete practices such as energy saving, waste reduction and recycling (Konstantopoulos et al., 2024). However, the likelihood of car usage increases with age (Herold et al., 2024; Konstantopoulos et al., 2024). In contrast, younger fans are more likely to use buses, indicating greater flexibility and cost sensitivity. While older audiences can often be reached through traditional media, younger fans should be addressed via digital platforms such as Instagram or TikTok (Konstantopoulos et al., 2024).

Team identification as a behavioural driver: A key finding concerns the role of team identification. Fans with strong emotional ties to their clubs are typically more active and loyal but also tend to cause higher emissions, for example due to frequent away travel, and they are less willing to pay for sustainable fan merchandise (Scharfenkamp & Wicker, 2024). At the same time strong identification can also have a positive effect: when sustainability aligns with fan identity, willingness to engage increases (Cayolla, Escadas, Mccullough, et al., 2023). Amann & Doidge (2023) further show that environmental communication is particularly effective when it appeals to collective identities, rivalries and the sense of community within fan cultures. Similarly, Gionfriddo et al. (2023) emphasize that messages evoking pride and belonging are more impactful than those based on guilt.

Environmental awareness and actual behaviour: Another central result is the widely documented gap between environmental awareness and actual behaviour, often referred to as the 'value-action-gap' (Konstantopoulos et al., 2024; Loewen & Wicker, 2021). While many fans express support for sustainability, implementation is often hindered by convenience, time constraints or lack of infrastructure. Especially in mobility decisions, environmental factors rarely serve as the primary determinant. Convenience, cost and time savings remain dominant (Dosumu et al., 2017; Konstantopoulos et al., 2024). This phenomenon can be explained through the low-cost hypothesis by Diekmann & Preisendörfer (2003), which says that environmental awareness translates into pro-environmental behaviour primarily in low-cost situations – those requiring minimal effort, time or money. When the perceived cost of sustainable action is high (e.g. price is too high or mean of transport takes too long), individuals won't act environmentally friendly. This helps explain why,

despite a public transport usage rate of approximately 50% in some studies, cars remain a major source of emissions in the context of fan mobility (Thormann & Wicker, 2024). Transport choices are strongly influenced by stadium location, parking availability and the quality of regional public transit, factors largely outside the clubs' control. This underscores the importance of supportive measures such as integrated ticketing, charging infrastructure and targeted information. This discrepancy between attitudes and actions is also evident in consumption. While many fans are generally open to sustainable products, actual usage such as choosing vegetarian meals, remains limited. Research shows that lower environmental knowledge and lower educational attainment correlate with reduced willingness to pay (Scharfenkamp & Wicker, 2024). This reveals a clear need for clubs to promote practical environmental literacy rather than merely communicating abstract values.

Effective communication for sustainable fan engagement: Strategic environmental communication by clubs emerges as a crucial tool for activating sustainable behaviour. Studies show that communication strategies are more effective when they resonate with fans' values, cultural practices and social identities. Particularly successful are messages that emphasize pride and community (Amann & Doidge, 2023), while moralizing or detached campaigns tend to fall flat. Clubs must design their communication formats not only to suit different age groups but also across multiple media channels. Traditional formats should be for older fans and digital content for younger audiences (Konstantopoulos et al., 2024). Moreover, communicating tangible actions is more effective than issuing general appeals, especially when fans can perceive the visible impact of their behaviour. Furthermore, Gionfriddo et al. (2023) recommend implementing environmental communication outside the stadium context and integrating it into the everyday lives of fans, since stadiums are emotionally charged environments where such messages are less likely to be effective.

The analysis reveals that sustainable behaviour in the context of football cannot be explained by a single factor. Instead, it results from a complex interplay of individual attitudes, social identity, demographic characteristics and structural conditions. This complexity highlights the need for differentiated strategies in environmental communication and behavioural design.

4.2 Limitations

This study has several limitations, primarily arising from the selection criteria used for the literature analysis. The restriction to English-language publications between 2015 and 2025 ensures the actuality of included studies but excludes potentially relevant research in other languages and regions. Likewise, the focus on professional football, Europe, and fans narrows the scope. This meant that significant studies from the United States or on other sports, as well as mixed data sets, were not included, limiting the transferability of findings. Geographical imbalances also remain: most European research stems from Western and Northern countries, while Eastern Europe is scarcely represented, mainly in multinational projects. This lack of geographical diversity constrains the applicability of results across the European context.

The exclusive focus on professional football is another limitation. Although this level produces the highest emissions, grassroots and amateur football dominate everyday participation worldwide and are rarely addressed. The limited number of studies included here also restricts representativeness, which calls for broader and more diverse study populations in future research.

Content- and method-related weaknesses of the included studies must also be considered. Most work focuses on mobility, while areas such as recycling, energy consumption, or waste remain understudied. Furthermore, a clear gender bias exists, as most surveys focus on middle-aged male fans, leaving the perspectives of women and of women's football underrepresented. This is

problematic, as research shows that women may differ in consumer and environmental behaviour, particularly regarding food choices.

Finally, methodological inconsistencies complicate comparability. Different approaches to calculating CO₂ emissions, varying inclusion of home and away matches, and limited transparency in data collection reduce reliability. Social desirability bias may also have influenced self-reported behaviours. Overall, these limitations highlight the need for more diverse, methodologically robust, and geographically inclusive studies, as well as closer collaboration between academics and football clubs to bridge the gap between research and practice.

5 Conclusion

This study highlights the complex relationship between football fans and clubs in the context of environmental sustainability. Fans contribute significantly to CO₂ emissions, mainly through travel and consumption, but they are also active stakeholders who can influence clubs and act as drivers of environmental change.

A key finding is that sustainable fan behaviour can only be achieved if appropriate structural conditions are in place. Appeals alone are insufficient: clubs must provide accessible and clearly communicated options that enable fans to act sustainably. If such structures are missing or poorly communicated, this may lead to frustration or rejection. Therefore, clubs should concentrate on areas they can directly influence, while collaborating with credible environmental initiatives that align with their identity. Communication must be strategic and tailored to the needs and values of distinct fan segments in order to support meaningful behavioural change.

For clubs, visible sustainability measures in stadium operations, positive and value-oriented communication, transparent strategies and incentives for sustainable mobility are particularly effective. Fan engagement is strongest when sustainability initiatives are credible, aligned with club identity and clearly communicated across multiple channels.

At the same time, research on this topic is still at an early stage. More studies are needed in underrepresented regions such as Eastern Europe, as well as stronger cooperation between academics and clubs to translate insights into practice. Future work should also address women's football and female fans, and employ more robust methodological approaches, including longitudinal and intervention studies, to assess the long-term impact of sustainability measures.

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